

standICT.eu 2026
ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

Standards Academy Webinar Insights from the European Standardisation Panel Survey

Maria Giuffrida

Senior Researcher Trust-IT Services & Deputy Coordinator of StandICT.eu 2026

21st May 2024

SPEAKERS

- Maria Giuffrida**
MODERATOR (Trust-IT Services, Italy)
- Knut Blind**
(Fraunhofer ISI & TU Berlin)
- Heejin Lee**
(Research Center for Digital Trade, Graduate School of International Studies, Yonsei University, Republic of Korea)
- Dirk Weiler**
(Nokia Head of Standards Policy)
- Daniel Fuchs**
(HU Berlin, BCCN)

standICT.eu 2026
ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

TRAINING WEBINAR
29th January 2024
16:00 - 18:00 (CET)

Geopolitics of ICT standardisation

In cooperation with
Berlin Contemporary China Network

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HSbooster.eu TRAINING ACADEMY **standICT.eu 2026**
ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

WEBINAR
1 Feb 2024
10:00 - 11:30 CET

Training Session 6

Standardisation in practice: When is the right time for standardisation in research processes?

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SPEAKERS

- Knut Blind**
Fraunhofer ISI and TU Berlin
- Jory Burson**
The Linux Foundation
- Mirko Böhm**
Linux Foundation Europe
- Silona Bonewald**
Leadingbit Solutions | IEEE (Former)
- Daniel Haack**
DIN e.V. - Digital Platforms
- Jochen Friedrich**
IBM

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ONLINE EVENT
18th March 2024
16:00 - 18:00 (CET)

Open Source & Standardisation

JOIN US!

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21 May 2024 14:00 – 16:00 CEST

Insights from the European Standardisation Panel Survey

Speakers and Agenda

- 14:00 - **Welcome & housekeeping**, Maria Giuffrida Trust-IT
- 14:05 - **The role of standardisation for knowledge valorisation**, Gergely Tardos (EC DG RTD)
- 14:25 **The role of research for standardisation at CEN/CENELEC**, Livia Mian (CEN/CENELEC)
- 14:45 - **Results and implications of the European Standardisation Panel**, Knut Blind (Fraunhofer ISI & TU Berlin)
- 15:15 **Recommendations derived from HSBooster**, Signe Annette Bøgh (Danish Standards)
- 15:35 - **Q&A and discussion**
- 16:00 - **Closure**

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27 May 2024 10:00 – 12:00 CEST

Geopolitics of ICT Standardisation

Focus on India

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The banner features a blue background with a white globe, a woman with a laptop, a checklist with checkmarks, and a stack of books.

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HSbooster.eu
Horizon Standardisation Booster

WEBINAR
6th June 2024
15:30 - 17:30 (CEST)

Human Rights & ICT Standardisation

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The banner features a background image of a brick wall with many security cameras mounted on it, and two people walking in the foreground.

[Register here](#)

Webinar Housekeeping

The event will be recorded and will be made available on the StandICT.eu website after the event (including the presentations of each speaker)

We do encourage you though to enter any question in the dedicated Q/A box placed in the lower toolbar. The speakers will be pleased to answer back your questions real-time

You can follow the chat to be informed and receive link on the main StandICT.eu outputs and publications.

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